

INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN LEARNING AND TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

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ABSTRACT

This passage gives an overview of importance of modern approach in acquiring language skills. Their effectiveness, teaching methods and scientists' ideas are given in this article as supportive examples.

In traditional language teaching methodologies, teachers teach facts from books. The teachers are seen as the main source of knowledge to the students. On the other hand, the new teaching methodologies focus on the teaching of strategies of deciding what information is needed. The teachers' roles are as guides or facilitators to help learners to be skilled in selecting, accessing, evaluating, organizing information. These strategies are important to manage vast amounts of information. The teachers also need to manage the time and courses and to construct knowledge autonomously in virtual learning communities. Besides performing this new role, the teacher is also the motivator of the whole learning process, and can facilitate intellectual group discussion. The teacher must reflect critically on the context of learning (mediated by technology), the methods (different than those used in the

classroom), the students, the teacher's own computer literacy (hardware, software and technical support needed), and other matters pertaining to digital literature. Learning via technology has many advantages. The Internet provides current and up-to-date data. It stores vast amount of information that can be retrieved quickly and easily. For language learning purposes, it provides text in authentic language, unlike the contrived language usually found in books.

In today's world information and communication technology ICT is becoming more and more major internet of topic in learning languages. ICT can be regarded as a new way of teaching and learning. The purpose of current academic work is the significance of ICT in learning languages plays a critical role either as EFL or ESL. Over the past years this issue was researched by myriad of linguists, technologists and PHD doctors. As a

consequence, all above mentioned people had the same point of view when it comes to the benefits of ICT in curriculum.

Asabere and Enguah 2012 defined ICT as the tools, facilities, processes, and equipments that provide the required environment with the physical infrastructure and the services for the generation, transmission.

Using ICT gives to learner's real life contact with, and exposure to the cultures of the people and countries where the new language is spoken and enables children to access and research information worldwide. Using ICT particularly, email, blogs and video conferencing facilitates children's real purpose and in real contexts. For example, with help of videos it is much easier to explain a student new word. Colorful pictures with translations from English or any other language to native (our Uzbek or Karakalpak) are very effective approaches to improve learner's range of vocabulary. Since majority of people especially children close to visual style of learning.

Interactive whiteboards, DVD's and the use of digital projectors may provide stimulating visual aids as a valuable strategy to support understanding and recall in the new language. ICT has the potential to increase the percentage of learning that involves the traditionally more difficult literacy skills by maximizing exposure to the written word.

By researchers was done the list of the most important achievements of ICT:

- Increase the quality of learning
- Ease of access to a very high volume of information
- Rapid access to information in very little time

- Indirect creation of learning experience
- Create an interest in learning
- Increase learning opportunities.

Quality of learning is the result of effective teaching so it is the most important thing in teaching and acquiring a skill. For instance, while explaining English grammar exactly tenses, articles or adjectives it is better to show texts, songs, short videos on relevant topics. Lessons at any educational establishments, particularly at schools, last very long. For this reason teacher must manage the time by giving full information about the unit. The only thing that may help her is handouts, Power Point Presentations. Conducting lessons with ICT does not mean that teachers must stop working over themselves. They must be prepared to go through a continuous learning process to improve teaching efficiency. This is because technology cannot replace good teaching but it can enhance it.

ICT helps English language learners by enabling them to communicate, edit, annotate and arrange text quickly and flexibly. Moreover, by using ICT learners can :

- access, select and interpret information
 - recognize patterns, relationships and behaviors
 - model, predict and hypothesis
 - test reliability and accuracy
 - review and modify their work to improve the quality
 - communicate with others and present information
 - evaluate their work
 - improve efficiency
 - be creative and take risks
 - gain confidence and independence.
- ICT can be used to integrate speaking,

listening, reading and writing. It enhances interactive teaching and learning styles. It also extends pupils' ability to exercise choice, work independently and make connections between their work in English and in other subjects.

ICT helps learners:

- use a wide range of strategies to explore contrasts, comparisons and connections dynamically
- annotate text in innovative ways
- enrich or broaden the context of literary study
- see texts in alternative versions
- use a wide range of analytical and critical techniques
- sort and process text and data quickly and efficiently
- order and arrange text and data experimentally, using combinations of word, image, sound and hypertext
- save, record, edit and adapt their work quickly and efficiently
- retain evidence of the editing process so that it can be examined
- change the organizational structure and qualities of texts to suit different audiences and purposes
- compose multi-authored texts
- select from a wider range of audiences, throughout the world
- exercise choice of medium and design while composing.

Michael Romano (2003) argues that there are growing numbers of students who are less motivated, less interested and less engaged in the process of learning. Teachers empowered with technology could make the classes as interesting as what happens in the world beyond the walls of the classroom. Teachers have to play their part to facilitate a learning environment that will open learners' minds

to new possibilities. As Zepp (2005) points out, teachers should relate the goals of education with effective use of ICT. In other words, teachers must be aware of the impact of technology on education and the required changes to enhance their teaching. They need to adjust their teaching process to suit this new ICT environment.

The advantages of ICT usage in foreign language teaching can be listed as:

Capacity to control presentation. This capacity marks the difference between computers and books. Books have a fixed presentation, unlike computers, which can combine visual with listening materials, text with graphics and pictures. 2. Novelty and creativity. A teacher may use different materials for each lesson, not like in teaching with textbooks, where all classes presenting a certain topic are the same. 3. Feedback. Computers provide a fast feedback to students' answers through error correction. It not only spots the mistake but also corrects it, sometimes even giving the appropriate advice. 4. Adaptability. Computer programs can be adapted by teachers to suit their students' needs and level of language knowledge (Padurean and Margan, 2009). There is significant evidence of the benefits and advantages that the use of ICT can have on learners. The effective use of ICT impacts on learners and various aspects of the learning process can be summarized as follows: ICT increases learners' motivation and thus enhances personal commitment and engagement; ICT improves independent learning. Learners' collaboration and communication are more important; Learners' attainment and outcomes are improved (Haucine, 2011).

As Zepp (2005) points out, teachers should relate the goals of education with effective use of ICT. In other words, teachers must be aware of the impact of technology on education and the required changes to enhance their teaching. They need to adjust their teaching process to suit this new ICT environment. The teacher's role in an ICT environment is that of a facilitator instead of being a purveyor of knowledge. This transformation from the old to the new method of delivering knowledge is a global phenomenon. Teaching then can be a transforming experience as it opens new windows to the world and creates a lifetime of opportunities. With ICT it implies the changes in the teacher's role not just as a teacher but as a monitor of participation and a practitioner of research, all of which possibilities are accelerated by the technological resources. Queiroz (2003) insists lecturers or teachers need to go through a continuous process of competency improvements to meet the demands of lifelong learning for their

professional development. Without this, teachers may be complacent and merely duplicate their practices electronically. If this happens, learners would not benefit from the technological advancements happening around them. To sum up, it is strongly believed that the implementation of educational technology and communication into EFL context provides flexible and diverse set of technological tools, promotes problem solving skills of students, gives chance learners to use higher order skills, develop critical thinking and effective information processing skills, encourages active independent, autonomous and collaborative language learning, motivates and facilitates language learning, enhances teacher training. On the contrary, it is clearly evident that the integration of ICT into language teaching practices has its own limits. ICTs should be integrated to foreign language teaching as an effective supplementary and a valuable complementary teaching

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